

Understanding chemistry of spermatozoa using NMR[†]

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In recent years, NMR has found wide applications, on one end to study the structure of molecules and on the other, to study intact body organs such as brain or heart. In between these two extremes is another fascinating branch of science, namely, the study of chemistry of intact cellular systems. While dedicated instruments for this type of work are not available, it is possible to use high field high resolution NMR spectrometers meant for molecular studies (e.g. a 300-500 MHz instrument) to obtain chemical and biological information on living cells. We have studied the chemistry of one of the important cellular systems, spermatozoa, using NMR. Spermatozoa play a key role in reproductive biology. Using techniques such as HSQC, it has been possible to obtain information on the ¹H and ¹³C NMR features of such cells. We have been able to detect a number of molecules in these sperm cells, which had evaded detection by conventional chemical tools. It has been possible to follow chemical pathways and kinetics of metabolism using conventional ¹³C NMR. ³¹P NMR provides valuable information on the energetics and pH profiles. Some of these studies have helped us to know how such cells can be activated or deactivated. For example, arginine deficiency is known to cause diseases such as oligospermia and asthenospermia. NMR experiments have established that the glycolysis and fructolysis of spermatozoa is activated by arginine. Arginine also increases synthesis of ATP, which is essential for sperm motility. The chemical information thus obtained has major biological implication for storage, activation and control of spermatozoa.

NMR spectroscopy is an indispensable tool in chemistry¹⁻³. Advances arising from the development of multi-dimensional Fourier Transform (FT) techniques, novel probe and magnet designs and fast data processing using work stations, have made it possible to overcome some of the limitations of the technique in handling problems in biology. With the currently achievable sensitivities, it is possible to detect molecules in concentrations of a few milli-molar. Use of 2- and 3-dimensional (2 and 3D) FT techniques allow adequate dispersion and enable assignments of individual resonances in spectra of molecules with molecular weights as large as 30000 Dalton^{4,5}. Intense peaks due to solvent (such as the strong ¹H resonance of H₂O in aqueous solutions) can be suppressed with high efficiencies, which enables one to work with resonances of interest⁶.

In view of these advances, it is now possible to understand chemical processes in living systems using NMR. Applications of NMR in biochemistry and biophysics cover three different aspects. One is the study of stereodynamics of biopolymers such as proteins and nucleic acids. Here, it is advantageous to use very high magnetic fields (spectrometers operating at fields up to 21 Tesla are commercially available) so as to obtain good dispersions of the chemically shifted ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N or ³¹P resonances using multidimensional NMR techniques. One can use NMR parameters such as chemical shifts, coupling constants and nuclear Overhauser effects to obtain structural information.

In conjunction with molecular modeling, study of the 3D structures and dynamics of biomolecules as well as their interaction with other molecules is now an active area of research. Here, NMR spectroscopy competes with X-Ray crystallography^{7,8}. Such investigations expand our 2D knowledge from genomics and proteomics (which deals with sequence information) into the 3D structures of nucleic acids and proteins. There are potential advantages of such studies in designing new drugs. NMR has been coupled to methods of combinatorial chemistry to speed up search for new bioactive compounds.

The second area is known as magnetic resonance imaging and spectroscopy (MRI and MRS)⁹. Here one uses a relatively lower magnetic field (1-2 T) but much larger magnets where whole animals and human being can be accommodated. One generally looks at an organ (e.g. brain or heart) and map the NMR properties of a single molecule (say ¹H in H₂O) in the form of its image (MRI). Alternatively, one can focus at a small volume of interest (typically 1 ml) and look at differences in the signal intensities of some key compounds (MRS). This way, one can diagnose diseases, identify healthy regions from diseased ones, follow changes following surgery or treatment by a drug. It is even possible to detect changes when a living being is doing a particular function¹⁰.

In this review, we focus on a third area called cellular NMR, whereby one can study the chemistry of living cells

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using NMR. Unlike in other two cases, dedicated instruments are not available for such studies. One utilizes spectrometers for molecular studies and design strategies to keep the cell alive while they are in the NMR spectrometer and to prevent them from settling in the sample tube. It is possible to analyze the chemical constituents of the cells, and study the metabolism while the cells are active. The changes in the kinetics of the metabolic processes under the influence of activators or drugs can be followed.

Using NMR, we have made extensive investigations on a particular group of cells called spermatozoa which play a key role in mammalian reproduction. Spermatozoa, unlike other cells, possess two specialized markers of activity, namely, motility and fertilizing ability. These provide opportunities for correlating chemical and metabolic measurements with cellular activity. Sperm motility can be beneficially or detrimentally influenced by a variety of physical and chemical factors¹¹⁻¹³. Implication of such studies in fertility regulation, artificial insemination, cellular and molecular biology and genetics of spermatozoa are well recognized. Most of the quality rating methods depend on either gross or microscopical morphological properties of the semen¹⁴. Also, methods are available to assess sperm motility qualitatively and quantitatively¹⁵⁻¹⁷ which are mostly based on *in vitro* analysis using biochemical techniques. Measurements of L-carnitine levels in the seminal plasma of men¹⁸ and measurement of apoptosis in spermatozoa¹⁹ are convenient methods for measuring semen quality. Conclusions derived from such studies may be influenced by the somewhat severe chemical treatments needed to isolate different metabolites. In this review, we propose to show how NMR can answer some of the vital questions on the chemistry of living cells which cannot be obtained by conventional biochemical methods and which generally involve destroying the cells.

Identification of small molecular weight compounds

NMR spectroscopy has been used in andrology for analysis of sample composition, kinetics of metabolites or structure of single components in studies related to semen, seminal plasma or spermatozoa²⁰. Composition and concentration of sperm cell and seminal fluid constituents vary dramatically from species to species²¹. For example, the most important compounds in boar seminal plasma are inositol, glycerophosphocholine (GPC), citrate and lactate²²⁻²⁴. Seminal plasma affects the quality of spermatozoa. Attempts have been made to determine full biochemical profile of seminal plasma using ¹H NMR²⁵. Lipid composition of human spermatozoa and seminal plasma has been studied using ¹H NMR and matrix-assisted laser desorption and ioniza-

tion time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS)²⁶. Reports on a number of mammalian species have shown the presence of carnitine, GPC, glutamic acid, citric acid, fructose, free amino acids, free fatty acids and inorganic phosphate (Pi)^{21,27-29} as well as proteins, sialic acid, glycogen and phospholipids in different segments of the epididymis³⁰.

Multinuclear NMR studies have been performed on aqueous solutions of lyophilysates of cell-free extract (CFE), epididymal fluid (EF) and on intact cells from caput and cauda regions of epididymis of sacrificed goats³¹. Several low molecular weight compounds present in different maturation phases of spermatozoa have been identified in the 600 MHz ¹H NMR spectra with the help of 2D homonuclear and heteronuclear correlation spectroscopy such as double quantum filtered correlation spectroscopy (DQF-COSY)³² and heteronuclear single quantum correlation spectroscopy (HSQC)³³. Homonuclear coupling constants have also been used to get unambiguous assignments of resonances. Attempts have been made to qualitatively analyze molecules/metabolites in the cells and in the EF, which help to identify abnormal or diseased state of cells and follow maturation of the cells. Fig. 1a shows the ¹H spectrum of CFE of the cells recovered from caput region. Fig. 1b and 1c show the corresponding regions of DQF-COSY. The identity of each molecule has been determined by making comparisons of the peak positions, *J*-connectivity patterns observed in these spectra and confirmed by HSQC spectrum as well as those reported in literature³⁴. Amino acids Ala, Arg, Asp, Gln, Glu, Ile, Leu, Lys, Met, Pro, Thr, Val, lactate, GPC, *m*-inositol, hypotaurine and aromatic molecules such as Phe, Tyr and UDPG could thus be identified. Similar strategy has been adopted for the assignment of ¹H and ¹³C resonance of CFE of cauda region and EF of cauda and caput regions of epididymis (Fig. 2a). ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts of thus identified molecules/metabolites are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Similarly, ¹H and ¹³C assignments have been carried out on intact cells from caput and cauda regions (Fig. 2b). As expected, NMR signals in cells are much broader and consequently lesser number of peaks could be observed. However, the spectral details correspond very well with those from cell extracts where a higher sensitivity could be achieved and give credence to conclusions derived from CFE. Presence of several amino acids, carbohydrates and lipids have been discussed in relation to their relevance to sperm functions. Presence of β -alanine and hypotaurine has been reported for the first time in goat epididymis³¹.

pH determination

Using ratiometric absorption technique, intracellular pH

Fig. 1. (a) 600 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum of CFE of spermatozoa from caput region of goat epididymis. (b) Upfield region of the DQF-COSY spectrum. The peaks are marked with one letter code and appropriate numbering scheme for amino acids and for other compounds, Lac, lactate; mI, *m*-inositol, Hyp, hypotaurine and GPC, glycerophosphocholine. (c) Down-field region of the same spectrum. Experimental parameters are : spectral width 7 KHz, 32 scans, relaxation delay 1.5 s and 2048 and 512 data points. The data were zero filled to 4K and 2K data points and apodized with a sine shifted window function of $\pi/3$ and $\pi/2$ for the F2 and F1 dimensions, respectively.

Fig. 2. (a) The upfield region of the gradient enhanced HSQC spectrum of CFE of spermatozoa from caput region of goat epididymis. (b) The upfield region of the gradient enhanced HSQC spectrum of intact spermatozoa from same region. Peaks are marked with the corresponding one letter code of amino acid and with appropriate number as per numbering scheme for amino acids and for other compounds. Experimental parameters are : relaxation delay 1.5 s, spectral width ¹H dimension 7 KHz, ¹³C dimension 13 KHz, 64 scans, 2048 and 400 data points in respective ¹H and ¹³C dimensions. The ¹³C decoupling was carried out during detection.

(pHi) has been directly correlated with sperm motility. Because of the dependence of the chemical shift of inorganic phosphate (Pi) on pH, NMR provides a non-invasive and accurate method for *in vivo* pH measurement. Using this method a slightly acidic cytosolic pH of 6.5–6.6 has been measured in bovine epididymal sperm³⁵. ³¹P NMR has been used to demonstrate the formation of high energy phosphate compounds by changes in pHi in sea urchin. At low pHi, when the cells are immotile and non-respiring, they accumulate phosphocreatine (PCr), and Pi level is low. When the pHi is high, sperm respiration and motility is high, PCr

Table 1. ^1H chemical shifts of resonances from different metabolites present in the CFE from caput region of goat epididymis

Compd.	C1H	C2H	C3H	C4H	C5H	C6H
GPC	3.64	3.77	3.94	4.31	3.67	3.20
Hyp	3.36	2.64				
Creatine		3.92		3.03		
<i>m</i> -Inositol	3.53	4.05	3.53	3.61	3.27	3.61
<i>s</i> -Inositol	3.32					
L(+)-Lactate		4.09	1.30			
α -Ala		3.78	1.46			
β -Ala		3.26	1.26			
Arg		3.76	1.92	1.64	3.23	
Asp		3.89	2.67, 2.79			
Gln		3.78	2.11	2.44		
Glu		3.71	2.04	2.37		
Gly		3.55				
His		3.99	3.18, 3.25			
Ile		3.67	1.96	1.45, 1.25	0.92, 0.99	
Leu		3.75	1.69	1.70	0.94, 0.95	
Lys		3.74	1.84	1.47	1.70	3.02
Met		3.85	2.12	2.63	CH ₃ 2.12	
Pro		4.12	2.26, 2.34	2.00	3.33, 3.41	
Tyr		3.95	3.17		7.16 (2,6)	6.91 (3,5)
Thr		3.58	4.26	1.31		
Ser		3.83	3.84			
Val		3.59	2.27	0.98, 1.03		

Table 2. ^{13}C chemical shifts of resonances from different metabolites present in the CFE from caput region of goat epididymis

Compd.	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
GPC	63.73	73.31	67.76	60.64	67.16	55.13
Hyp	34.66	56.62				
Creatine		55.01		38.13		
<i>m</i> -Inositol	72.32	73.40	72.32	73.67	75.53	73.67
<i>s</i> -Inositol	74.81					
L(+)-Lactate		69.73	21.21			
α -Ala		51.71	17.26			
β -Ala		47.86	9.39			
Arg		55.80	28.55	24.94	41.69	
Asp		53.37	37.59			
Gln		55.48	27.94	31.95		
Glu		55.41	27.84	31.87		
Gly		42.61				
His		55.69	28.5			
Ile		60.79	36.81	25.43	12.10, 15.80	
Leu		55.85	40.76	25.02	21.83, 23.05	
Lys		55.77	30.80	22.36	27.30	40.23
Met		55.22	30.60	29.89	CH ₃ 15.01	
Ser		61.44	57.58			
Tyr		57.30	36.57			
Thr		61.50	67.30	20.70		
Pro		62.45	30.05	24.80	47.23	
Val		61.61	30.30	17.80, 19.07		

goes down and Pi increases. This change is reversible³⁶. It has been shown that depression of pHi using weak acids can reversibly inhibit sperm motility³⁷. Changes in cell pH as a function of time, during glycolysis of cells incubated with different amounts of arginine have been measured. For identical conditions (i.e. number of cells, temperature, viability, motility, pH etc.), the relative rate of change in pH increases up to certain concentration of L-arginine and declines thereafter³⁸.

Metabolism and activation by arginine

Glycolysis and respiration constitute the main sources of energy for motility in mammalian spermatozoa. The chain of reactions which leads from fructose/glucose to lactic acid under anaerobic conditions is diagrammatically shown in Fig. 3. ³¹P and ¹H NMR have been used to monitor changes of various metabolites, such as ADP, ATP, GPC etc. having high energy bonds before and after the activation of motility in turbot spermatozoa (*Psetta maxima*)³⁹. Similar observation has been reported in case of bull, hamster, boar, ram and goat^{40,41}. However, no high energy molecules such as phosphoarginine or phosphocreatine which could act as energy shuttles have been observed. Spermatozoa possess capability to stand starvation which can be further activated by using appropriate substrate such as glucose, fructose or pyruvate⁴².

Presence of free amino acids in seminal plasma plays important role on spermatozoal metabolism and motili-

Fig. 3. Diagrammatic representation of metabolic pathways for glucose/fructose present in spermatozoa under anaerobic conditions.

ty^{43,44}. In particular, deficiency of L-arginine leads to derangement of metabolism of tissues undergoing mitosis⁴⁵. L-Arginine plays an important role in stimulating spermatozoa^{46,47} and exhibits beneficial effects on the sperm count and motility in oligospermic and asthenospermic patients^{48,49}. Using NMR it has been shown that arginine has several beneficial roles in the efficacy and preservation of spermatozoa^{38,50,51}. Small concentrations of arginine enhances the metabolic rate and the synthesis of ATP. Fig. 4a depicts ³¹P NMR spectrum of spermatozoa undergoing glycolysis. Fig. 4b shows spectrum of cells undergoing glycolysis which have been incubated with 10 mM of L-arginine. It is observed that ATP signals build up with glycolysis and Pi signal shifts with a concomitant loss in intensity. A progressive up-field shift of the Pi signal can be ascribed to the acidification of the extra- and intracellular environment due to formation of lactic acid during metabolism⁵². The enhancement of ATP signal is indicative of higher phosphorylation rate in presence of arginine.

Fig. 4. ³¹P NMR spectrum of spermatozoa from the cauda region of epididymis of goat (a) cells undergoing glycolysis in Dullbecco's medium (initial pH 7.2), containing 10% (w/v) glucose but no arginine, (b) cells undergoing glycolysis after incubation with L-arginine (10 mM) for 30 min. Spectral parameters are : 2 s relaxation delay, 10 μ s pulse width, 10 KHz spectral width and 512 transients with power-gated broad-band proton decoupling.

Fig. 5 shows the relevant portion of ¹³C NMR of spermatozoa incubated with 1-¹³C glucose. Glucose consumption and lactate production by cells during glycolysis show (inset figure) that the rates of glucose consumption and lactate generation increase monotonically with L-arginine until certain concentration. The maximum increase in the glycolytic rate is six to seven times that of control³⁸. L-Ornithine, which lacks guanidino group and has similar chain-length is unable to induce significant stimulations in metabolic rates. L-Arginine itself does not get metabolized by the cells but only acts as an activator. Binding of arginine

Fig. 5. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of intact spermatozoa. Cells were incubated with $1\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ labeled glucose and spectrum was recorded after 2 h of glucose addition. Spectral parameters are 25 kHz spectral width, 60° flip angle, 2 s relaxation delay and 1024 transients with power-gated broad-band proton decoupling. Inset figure shows rate constant of glucose consumption and that of lactate production for different concentrations of L-arginine. The data was fitted to a first order rate equation (decaying) to determine the rate constant for substrate consumption whereas for lactate generation a rising exponential equation was used for the calculation of the rate constant (■) Represent the glucose consumption rate constant and (□) lactate production rate

involves the guanidino group end of the amino acid³⁸. The observation is in agreement with the report⁴⁷, in which competitive experiments with L-arginine and analogs established the active role of guanidino group in L-arginine transport across the sperm cell.

Iodoacetate and iodoacetamide, known metabolic inhibitor, block the formation of lactate or ethanol anaerobically by suppressing the production of NADH required for the reduction of pyruvate or acetaldehyde⁵³⁻⁵⁵. Motility of spermatozoa is diminished by treatment with these inhibitors under aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Treatment of inhibitor impaired cells with arginine retrieves the glycolytic activity⁵⁰. The extent of retrieval is inversely related to the extent of inhibition. Pre-incubation of cells with arginine before subjecting to the inhibitor (Fig. 6) more or less nullifies the inhibition of glycolysis as compared to the cells post-treated with arginine. Thus, if arginine is already present in the cell suspension, the glycolytic activity of cells is less affected by inhibitors. ^{31}P NMR reveals that ATP level decreases with time on treatment with inhibitor as compared

Fig. 6. Protective action of L-arginine against iodoacetic acid inhibitor in spermatozoa. Filled bars represent the change in ^{13}C lactate signal intensity after 120 min of incubation in presence of iodoacetic acid and crossed bars after treating with L-arginine (20 mM) for 20 min before incubation with iodoacetic acid (pre-treatment). Cells were incubated with different concentration of iodoacetic acid for 20 min. Then $1\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ glucose was added and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded with time. Lactate signal of subsequent spectra were integrated and are expressed with respect to the glucose signal of first spectrum which is assigned a value of 100. Inset figure shows effect of various amino acids on the glycolytic rate of iodoacetic acid impaired spermatozoa. Change in the ^{13}C lactate signal intensity after 120 min (A) control cells, (B) cells incubated with 0.6 mM of iodoacetic acid, cells incubated with 0.6 mM of iodoacetic acid followed by 20 mM of (C) L-arginine, (D) D-arginine, (E) L-nitroarginine, (F) L-homoarginine, (G) L-lysine and (H) L-ornithine for 20 min. For other details see the caption of Fig. 5

to the cells having full glycolytic activity. However, following addition of L-arginine, ATP level builds up with time⁵⁰. Only arginine (both D and L configuration) can retrieve the glycolytic activity and other amino acids are ineffective (inset figure). Arginine can thus be used to enhance the motility and activity of sperms in cases where certain conditions in the body make them immotile leading to involuntary infertility. It may also be tested as a probable therapeutic agent for reversing the effect of different contraceptive agents.

Maturation

Epididymis, the male reproductive organ acts as a highly efficient storage organ enabling spermatozoa to preserve their motility and fertilizing potential. There are three main parts of the epididymis: caput the birth place of spermatozoa, corpus where spermatozoa are in a semi-matured state and cauda containing fully matured spermatozoa. During the passage through the epididymis, spermatozoa undergo major morphological and biochemical changes, collectively regarded as maturation. Epididymis also provides fluid environment of special composition to promote maturation⁵⁶,

which is a prerequisite for sperm motility and fertilizing ability and finally helps in the disposal of aging and superfluous spermatozoa. Epididymis makes an important contribution to the plasma membrane alterations of the cells that occur during transit of spermatozoa. Correlation between changes in rat sperm membrane lipids, protein and the physical state of membrane during epididymal maturation has been reported⁵⁷. Fig. 7 shows ³¹P NMR of sperms from cauda, corpus and caput regions of goat epididymis. It

Fig. 7. 202.15 MHz ³¹P NMR spectra of spermatozoa obtained from caput, corpus and cauda regions of goat epididymis. Assignments have been indicated for all the signals⁴².

is observed that for same number of cells and experimental conditions the ATP signal intensity increases in the order, cauda > corpus > caput, at the expense of inorganic phosphate (Pi). This follows the trend of maturation of these cells as they descent from caput → corpus → cauda region of epididymis¹¹. It has been shown that factors responsible for forward motility occur in the cauda region of the epididymis. While some materials are localized in the cauda epididymis and are involved in sperm motility, external factors also seem to be involved in enhancing, inducing and effecting sperm motility.

Capacitation

Prior to fertilization mammalian spermatozoa undergo physiological changes in the female reproductive tract^{58,59}. These changes are collectively known as capacitation. Several attempts have been made to eliminate the female tract

as the sole locus for capacitation. In some species, capacitation has been achieved *in vitro* following a variety of chemical treatments⁶⁰⁻⁶². Ca²⁺ ion is an essential requirement for motility, maintenance/activation and for the initiation of acrosome reaction^{63,64}. Capacitation is not observed if calcium ions which are major component of the capacitation medium are not present⁶⁴. The results on goat spermatozoa from cauda region of epididymis are shown in Fig. 8. The ³¹P NMR at different time intervals indicate *in vitro* ca-

Fig. 8. 202.15 MHz ³¹P NMR spectra of spermatozoa obtained from cauda region of goat epididymis at different time intervals under *in vitro* capacitation⁴².

pacitation in Krebs-Ringer bicarbonate buffer. One observes that ATP and sugar phosphate signals increase at the expense of Pi with increasing periods of capacitation. A period of 3 h capacitation is optimum as the ATP signals start to deteriorate thereafter⁶⁵. These observations suggest that not only is capacitation in the female tract essential for the act of fertilization, but also the duration has to be optimal. These results are in good agreement with the observation that 3 h incubation for epididymal and 4 h for ejaculated spermatozoa in Krebs-Ringer bicarbonate buffer containing pyruvate and lactate is required for the capacitation and acrosome reaction to take place.

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